

Radiological Underestimation of Tumor Response After Neoadjuvant Pembrolizumab in MSI-High Colon Cancer: Implications for Surgical Management

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Introduction

Neoadjuvant immunotherapy with immune checkpoint inhibitors like pembrolizumab is an emerging treatment approach for mismatch repair-deficient (dMMR)/microsatellite instability-high (MSI-H) colorectal cancer. However, its role in locally advanced disease remains unclear, especially regarding the accuracy of post-treatment imaging and its correlation with surgical pathology. We present a case of neoadjuvant pembrolizumab achieving complete pathological response despite ambiguous radiological findings.

Case Presentation

A 29-year-old female, with a family history of colorectal and endometrial cancers, presented with a symptomatic ascending colon tumor, raising suspicion for Lynch syndrome. Imaging staged the tumor as cT4aN2M0. Immunohistochemistry of the biopsy demonstrated loss of MLH1 and PMS2 (MMR Proteins), confirming MSI-H/dMMR adenocarcinoma, while germline testing for Lynch Syndrome was negative. The patient received 10 cycles of neoadjuvant pembrolizumab. Post-treatment contrast-enhanced CT indicated minimal reduction of the primary tumor with persistent bulky lymphadenopathy, suggesting a limited treatment response and supporting the decision for surgical resection. A right hemicolectomy was performed with curative intent. Gross examination revealed a firm, pearly white and ulcerated semi-circumferential tumor bed. Remarkably, histopathology demonstrated a complete pathological response (pTxN0LOV0Pn0), with no residual tumor or lymph node involvement. The tumor bed showed fibrosis with scattered microcalcifications, which was consistent with tissue healing. This case highlights the possibility that radiological findings may underestimate tumor response following neoadjuvant immunotherapy, where immune infiltration and stromal remodeling may mimic residual disease. From a surgical perspective, this suggests important considerations regarding patient selection and timing of resection.

Conclusion

Neoadjuvant immunotherapy may redefine treatment for selected dMMR/MSI-H patients with complete tumor eradication before surgery. This case suggests that conventional imaging may underestimate response after neoadjuvant immunotherapy in selected dMMR/MSI-H colon cancers and highlights the need for further prospective studies to better define the role of surgery and identify reliable response biomarkers.

Keywords

MSI-H colorectal cancer, dMMR, Pembrolizumab, Neoadjuvant, immunotherapy, Immune checkpoint inhibitors, Pseudoprogression, Colon cancer